

THE PLACE AND ROLE OF SOCIAL NETWORKS IN THE FORMATION OF SOCIAL ATTITUDES OF YOUNG PEOPLE

Rayimkulov Bakhtiyor

Trainee teacher of Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236149>

Abstract. *This article examines the influence of social networks on the formation of young people as individuals in social relations. As the Internet, that is, social networks, has become a very powerful source of information today, it plays an important role in the promotion and propaganda of ideological and ideological threats on a global scale. With the help of social networks, the heart, mind and spirituality of young people are being severely derailed. That's why we should not ignore the increasing development of various ideological and informational attacks. It is necessary to use social networks in the right way to bring up the future generation to be spiritually mature and healthy.*

Key words: *Globalization, personality, ideology, internet, social network, spirituality, community development.*

МЕСТО И РОЛЬ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ СЕТЕЙ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ УСТАНОВОК МОЛОДЕЖИ

Аннотация. *В данной статье рассматривается влияние социальных сетей на формирование молодежи как личности в социальных отношениях. Поскольку Интернет, то есть социальные сети, сегодня стал очень мощным источником информации, он играет важную роль в продвижении и пропаганде идеологических и идеологических угроз в глобальном масштабе. С помощью социальных сетей сильно подрываются сердце, разум и духовность молодых людей. Поэтому не следует игнорировать возрастающее развитие различных идеологических и информационных атак. Необходимо правильно использовать социальные сети, чтобы воспитать будущее поколение духовно зрелым и здоровым.*

Ключевые слова: *Глобализация, личность, идеология, Интернет, социальная сеть, духовность, развитие сообщества.*

One of the greatest discoveries of the 20th century was the international network, the Internet. This network has overtaken television, radio, newspapers and magazines in a short period of time. Countless people around the world are using the Internet to share information, improve their knowledge, and solve various problems instantly. Today, regardless of age, social group or

class, the number of Internet users is increasing, and the number of students is increasing, which requires clarification and promotion work in this area.

Relationships of certain social groups to which he belongs also have an impact on the formation of a person's psychology. In the process of such interaction and communication, together with the influence of individuals on each other, they influence their views and social institutions in relation to society, work, people, and their personal qualities. will be Living in a certain social environment, a person acquires a unique place, reputation, and role there.

A person is not only the object of social relations, but also its subject and active participant.

A person is a concrete person, a representative of a certain state, society, group (this group can be social, ethnic, religious, political, age-related, etc.), able to establish a conscious relationship with others, consciously act is a person who can walk, who can show his unique human image in all relationships, and who has unique individual and social characteristics.

The intensity of today's time shows that our life cannot be imagined without the Internet or social networks. Most of the people's activities are related to being aware of the daily news happening in the world through the Internet, social networks and telegram channels, and transmitting them to each other.

As of today, the number of pages "promoting" spiritual and moral depravity in the social network of the Internet system is more than a few hundred million, which worries humanity even more. Chingiz Aitmatov writes about this: "There is no need to put a camel's skin on a man's bald head. The wars that take place now do not take place on the battlefield, but in the ideological training ground. From this point of view, it is a great tragedy that young people waste a lot of time on the Internet. Because in the process of globalization, It is also seen when the scope of ideological influence is greatly expanded and accelerated to an incomparable level. otherwise, it is impossible to withstand various spiritual threats, their sometimes overt and sometimes hidden influence.

Not everyone knows that the concept of "social network" appeared in 1954 and, of course, has nothing to do with the Internet, and they began to study this phenomenon in the 30s of the last century. This concept was introduced by sociologist James Barnes: "social network" is a social structure consisting of a group of nodes with social objects (people or organizations) and connections between them (social relations). In simpler terms, this is a certain group of familiar people, where the person himself is the center, and his friends are the branches. All members of the network have two-way or one-way connections. For example, it could be a group of students where a certain Jack is the center and Bill and Kathryn are his acquaintances (branches). Gradually, the scientific concept gained popularity first in developed capitalist countries and then in Eastern

Europe. With the development of society, we came to the information age, during which we created many types of communication, which led to a leap in the development of social networks, and now this scientific concept is used everywhere.

Sources define a social network as an online platform that people use to communicate and create social relationships with other people based on similar interests. For the first time, the e-mail form of the social network appeared as a means of communication between people. This was the first appearance of communication through computer networks. Originally created for the exchange of information between two people, electronic communication later became a means of communication between groups. Scientists R.Solomonoff and A.Rapoport, who first expressed their ideas about social networks, expressed their opinion about the virtual form of communication in the middle of the last century. Hungarian experts P.Erdos and A.Renilar have shared their ideas about the formation of social networks. In 1954, J. Barnes, one of the representatives of the Manchester school, introduced the term social network into scientific sources as a separate concept. Scientists attribute the growth and development of communication between people on the Internet to the rapid activity of social networks. Actually it is. You can establish fast and convenient communication in the virtual world at any time of the day or night. You can write, talk and see your interlocutor. All you need is a computer or phone and the Internet.

In order to change people's consciousness and worldview through social networks, situations such as ideological and ideological influence, distribution of disinformation, especially require vigilance. In the information attack, the human mind and the psyche of the nation are targeted. Basically, the idea of ideological influence by conquering the human mind and heart lies in the implementation of information attacks. This situation undermines the stability of the states and endangers the nation's historically formed values, its identity, survival as a nation and people. Every compatriot, first of all, young representatives of the generation will have to understand deeply.

Today, the majority of Internet users are young people, and most of them are students. Therefore, it is emphasized that these new technologies have a negative impact on the education of children and young people if they are not given advice, instructions or are not completely controlled by experts, doctors, pedagogues, and scientists. Because today's globalization process, the "race" of active use of various information fields to capture the spiritual world of young people is accelerating.

Today, our society is interested in educating a new generation of enterprising reformers, strategic thinkers, educated and qualified personnel. Therefore, from kindergarten to higher education, all stages of education are being reformed. Therefore, in order to increase the

knowledge and level of not only today's youth, but also the members of our society as a whole, first of all, knowledge and high spirituality are needed.

Conclusion: In conclusion, as stated by the head of our state, Shavkat Mirziyoev, "... we do not base our children's minds and worldviews on the basis of our world and national literature, which is a treasure of high spirituality, which has been tested for centuries, but on the basis of some dubious and harmful information. we cannot ignore its formation on the basis of it".

Therefore, today's era demands that we do not give any chance to the various negative situations in social networks that are trying to deceive our youth by spreading slander and fabrications on a global scale. After all, it is our main task to raise our youth in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland and to increase their love for their people and country by protecting our national spirituality. No matter how hard we try, we cannot stop our youth from using social networks. It is appropriate to use a different solution. That is, we need to teach young people how to use social networks. It is better to prevent future events than to wait for future events.

REFERENCES

1. Yahyo Muhammad Amin. Internetdagi tahdidlardan himoya T.: "Movaraunnahr", 2016.
2. Таранов П. Энциклопедия высокого ума. М., 1999,
3. Ro'zimatov, J. (2024). BO 'LAJAK BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O'QITUVCHILARINING RAQAMLI TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISH METODIKASINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 4 (4), 141-146.
4. Rajabov H.I. "Globallashuv sharoitida axborot tahdidlariga qarshi kurashishning zamonaviy texnologiyalarini yaratish muammolari" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiya materiallari T.: "Fan va texnologiya" 2020 yil
5. Rajabov H.I. "Globallashuv sharoitida axborot tahdidlariga qarshi kurashishning zamonaviy texnologiyalarini yaratish muammolari" mavzusidagi xalqaro ilmiy-amaliy konferentsiya materiallari T: 2020 yil,
6. Ruzimatov, J. (2024). THE ROLE OF USING DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES IN METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF FUTURE PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS. *Евразийский журнал академических исследований*, 4(3 Part 2), 109-113.
7. Ro'zimatov, J. (2024). BO 'LAJAK BOSHLANG 'ICH SINF O'QITUVCHILARINING RAQAMLI TA'LIM TEXNOLOGIYALARIDAN FOYDALANISHNING AFZALLIGI. *Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences* , 3 (8), 72-78.

8. Ro‘zimatov, J., Norbo‘tayeva, O., Savrullayeva, M., Cho‘liyeva, A., & Usmonova, G. (2024). THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(5), 480-484.